

Rolling angles recovery of flowing cells in holographic tomography exploiting the phase similarity

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Abstract

Traditional tomographic reconstruction methods are based on the knowledge of illumination directions or rotation angles of imaged biological samples. Recently, phase contrast tomographic flow cytometry by digital holography has been demonstrated to reconstruct the three-dimensional refractive index distribution of single cells while they are flowing along microfluidic channels. In this system, the illumination direction is fixed while the sample's rotation is not deterministically known *a priori* but induced by hydrodynamic forces. We propose here a technique to retrieve the rolling angles, based on a new phase images similarity metric that is capable to identify cell's orientations from its 3D positioning while it is flowing along the microfluidic channel. The method is experimentally tested and also validated through appropriate numerical simulations. We provide demonstration of concept by achieving reconstruction of breast cancer cells tomography.

1. Introduction

Holographic tomography (HT) is a label-free optical microscopy technique with several applications in bioimaging. It is complementary to fluorescence imaging but has no limitations due to photobleaching and phototoxicity [1-3]. HT allows to reconstruct the three-dimensional (3D) refractive index (RI) distribution of a biological specimen by using two-dimensional (2D) quantitative phase measurements of its complex scattered fields [4,5], thus recovering its full 3D morphological information. Knowledge of the angles at which the probing beam illuminates the sample during image recording is the fundamental requirement to reconstruct its tomogram. To date, the methods used to record 2D images for 3D HT of microscopic objects are mainly two, i.e., variation of the illumination beam direction with fixed sample [6-9] and mechanical [10] or optical [11] sample's rotation with fixed illumination beam direction. These methods show different limitations that can reduce the accuracy of the tomographic reconstruction [3]. The first technique is characterized by limited illumination angles (up to 150°). The second one provides limited throughput and the sample can be altered by external forces used to rotate it. To overcome these issues, in [12] an alternate tomographic method has been proposed where hydrodynamic forces, generated by a laminar flow in a microfluidic channel, induce full sample's rotation (i.e. 360°). A fixed beam within a holographic imaging set-up illuminates the rolling sample. Noteworthy, *a priori* knowledge about the positions and the illumination angles of the rolling cells along the microfluidic channel is not

needed, because they are estimated from the combined use of *a priori* information about the hydrodynamic flow and the data. Currently, three different numerical methods have been developed to recover the unknown rolling angles [12,13], depending on the shape and RI content of the imaged sample. The first one was developed for cells with quasi-homogenous RI distribution and demonstrated for red blood cells (RBCs). This approach models RBCs as microlenses [14], thus providing a mathematical relationship between the rolling angles and the variation of Zernike coefficients during the cell rotation. The second one was developed for cells having high RI variations such as diatoms [12]. In this case, the maximization of the Spatial Correlation Coefficient (SCC) between pairs of mirrored phase images permits the rolling angles identification of each pair such that the angles sum is 180° . However, aforementioned recovery methods work efficiently for cells having non-spherical shapes as in the case of RBCs and diatoms. Therefore, a third approach was investigated for quasi-spherical cells [13] which exploits information deduced from a theoretical microfluidic model of cell rotation and centroids movement. This last method was also demonstrated for clusters of tumour cells. Other solutions to perform tomographic reconstructions with partial information about the rotating angles or illumination directions have been proposed, mainly focusing on the tomographic reconstruction tolerance with respect to the lack of knowledge [15,16] or illumination errors [17]. Here we propose a new rolling angle recovery method, based on a new phase images similarity metric that exploits the local contrast image measurement through the Tamura Coefficient (TC) [18]. In particular, it is able to recognize cell orientations from its 3D positions within the microfluidic channel. Actually, since the flow velocity gradient induces the rotation for cells flowing not at the channel centre, the latter can be considered for investigation. The cell's positioning within the channel's cross section is almost constant, thus ensuring continuous and quasi-uniform cell rotation. An accurate 3D tracking of flowing cells would enable the calculation of rolling angle increments. In fact, we can safely suppose that they are proportional to the cell movement along the flow direction, providing the information required by the tomographic algorithm. To this end, similarity metrics could be exploited. In this paper, we demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed similarity metrics and validate it through numerical simulations of a 3D rotating cell phantom in a microfluidic channel to have a full control of the setup parameters and a reliable reference. Moreover, the robustness with respect to the shape, noise levels and RIs variation is numerically investigated. Then, a comparison with other well-known image similarity metrics is presented to show the superiority of the proposed approach. Finally, two proof of concept experimental cases are analysed reporting tomographic reconstructions of breast cancer cells (MCF-7), obtained by using the proposed rolling angles recovery approach.

2. The HT recording system

In this Section, the HT system setup to perform the tomographic reconstruction of rolling cells in continuous flow is presented. A classical digital holography (DH) microscope based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer for the quantitative imaging of biological samples is employed. The light source is a 400 mW fiber-coupled laser at 532 nm, whose beam is divided into two parts, i.e., an object wave and a reference wave. The object wave illuminates the sample within a microfluidic channel and, after passing through a microscope objective (oil-immersion 40 \times , numerical aperture 1.30, Plan-Apochromat), it interferes with the reference wave in the beam-splitter. The interference fringe pattern, i.e. the digital hologram, propagates up to a 2048 \times 2048 CCD camera (USB 3.0 u-eye, from IDS), recording at 35 fps. The biological sample is inserted in a syringe activated by a controlled microfluidic pump that realizes a flux at 7 nL/s through a commercial microfluidic channel (PMMA polymeric material with cross section 200 μm \times 200 μm and length 7 cm). In Fig. 1(a), the sketch of the HT system is reported, while Fig. 1(b) shows the parabolic velocity profile in a channel section. The red rectangle in Fig. 1(b) highlights the region wherein the flowing cells are usually observed and recorded. Thanks

to the parabolic velocity profile, a cell flowing not at the channel centre undergoes a torque generated by the velocity gradient that induces a rotation [19]. Given a reference system with the y axis along the flow direction as in Fig. 1(c), the cells can be assumed to move along the y axis and rotate around the x axis as sketched in Fig. 1(c). The HT records flowing and rolling cells as reported in the example in Fig. 1(d) wherein three cuts of the recorded digital holograms of the same MCF-7 cell, at different time frames, are reported. In particular, in the left image, the shape of the cell appears elongated in the y direction, while, in the right one, the flipped elongation in the y direction demonstrates the rolling around the x axis.

Fig. 1. Opto-fluidic system. (a) Sketch of the holographic microscope. OFs, Optical Fibers; MO, Microscope Objective; M, Mirror; BS, Beam-Splitter. (b) Parabolic velocity profile in the cross section of the microfluidic channel. The red rectangle is the region in which cells are recorded. (c) Scheme of rotation of cells due to the velocity gradient and chosen reference coordinate system. (d) Three cuts of digital holograms of the same MCF-7 cell at different time frames. The shape variation of the cell highlights its rotation around the x axis while it is flowing along the y axis. (e,f) Tracking of the cell in (d) within the channel's sections xy and yz, respectively.

As mentioned in the Introduction, to make the tomographic reconstruction possible, the 3D tracking of cells is needed [18]. This process consists of two main steps, i.e. the numerical refocusing of the detected cell in each recorded frame, to calculate the position along the z axis, and the transversal localization. The numerical refocusing is usually performed by minimizing a suitable image contrast metric, calculated on the amplitude reconstruction. In our case, the TC is used [18], defined as

$$TC\{A\} = \sqrt{\sigma\{A\}/\mu\{A\}} \quad (1)$$

where σ and μ are the standard deviation and the average operators, respectively, and A is the amplitude reconstruction. Instead, the transversal localization is obtained by using the weighted centroid calculated on refocused quantitative phase maps (QPMs). In Fig. 1(e,f) we report the 3D tracking of the cell in Fig. 1(d), visualizing the trajectory within the xy and yz sections, respectively, as a result of the above steps. It is noted that, the cell drift in Fig. 1(e,f), evaluated as the standard deviation of the estimated positions along the x and z axes (σ_x and σ_z , respectively) is negligible, being $\sigma_x = 0.31 \mu\text{m}$ and

$\sigma_z = 0.77 \mu\text{m}$. This demonstrates the quasi-constant positioning within the channel's cross section xz , a key point to assume the quasi-uniform cell rotation.

3. The proposed rolling angles recovery method

In our HT system, the beam direction is fixed while the sample flows and rotates along the microfluidic channel, without the explicit knowledge about its 3D pose. Actually, a suitable method is needed to calculate the 3D positions and 3D orientations of the samples exploiting information extracted from the acquired data. Nevertheless, the approach to estimate them must be properly conceived to make the tomographic reconstructions reliable. Some a priori information is available on the geometry of the microfluidic channel and on the flow. In particular, since the length of the channel (7 cm) is much greater than the size of the cross section ($200 \mu\text{m} \times 200 \mu\text{m}$), the cells move along the flow direction y while keeping their positions within each cross section quasi-constant within the Field Of View (FOV) (approximately $175 \mu\text{m} \times 175 \mu\text{m}$), as demonstrated in the example of Fig. 1(d-f). The translational and rotational velocities of each cell can be considered continuous and quasi-uniform, with values that depend on the initial 3D position of cells. Therefore, for each recorded holographic sequence of a rolling cell, it is possible, in principle, to estimate the incremental rolling angle of a certain frame with respect to the previous one as a function of the cell position movement along y axis only. The above assumptions aim at keeping the model as simple as possible, compatibly with the expected performance. Hence a theoretical microfluidic model is not needed any more as in [13]. Let us assume that a sequence of K digital holograms of a flowing cell has been recorded. After calculating the 3D positioning of the cell (x_k, y_k, z_k) for the k -th frame, through the holographic tracking strategy described above, and reconstructing the corresponding QPMs, the proposed method recovers the rolling angles according to the following three steps.

- i. 3D realignment of the QPMs with respect to the 3D positions.
- ii. Estimation of the frame index f_{180} at which the 180° of rotation occurs with respect to the QPM of the frame $k = 1$.
- iii. By assuming the proportionality between translation and rotation, and a null initial rotation angle $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$ for the frame $k = 1$, the rolling angle is calculated, for each frame $k = 2, 3, \dots, K$, a

$$\theta_k = 180^\circ \frac{y_k - y_1}{y_{f_{180}} - y_1}. \quad (2)$$

The key-enabling step is the identification of a phase image rotated by 180° with respect to the first one. Here, the Tamura's Similarity Index (TSI) is proposed as the QPMs similarity metric used to solve this problem, since it is expected to exhibit more robustness against other possible metrics. TSI is based on local measurements of the image contrast through the TC. In particular, let $QPM(k)$ the phase reconstruction of the k -th frame with sizes $N \times M$, and $S_{i,j}(k)$ a 3×3 patch within $QPM(k)$, centred in the pixel of coordinates (i,j) , with $i = 2, \dots, N-1$ and $j = 2, \dots, M-1$. By replacing each pixel of the $QPM(k)$ with the contrast value of $S_{i,j}(k)$ calculated by using TC, we obtain a new image of sizes $(N-2) \times (M-2)$, namely the local contrast image (LCI), whose generic element is

$$LCI_{i,j}(k) = TC \{S_{i,j}(k)\} \quad (3)$$

with $i = 2, \dots, N-1, j = 2, \dots, M-1$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$. Finally, the TSI is obtained as follows

$$TSI(k) = TC \{LCI(1) ./ flip\{LCI(k)\}\} \quad (4)$$

where $flip$ is the vertical flipping operator to take into account the mirroring property with respect to the x -axis and $./$ denotes an elementwise division. $TSI(k)$ defines a functional whose global minimum point

$$f_{180} = \arg \min_k \{TSI(k)\} \quad (5)$$

is the sought for index f_{180} . Once f_{180} is estimated, a full tomographic algorithm can be applied.

4. The proposed rolling angles recovery method

To assess the performance of TSI, we compare it with some of the most used similarity indices, i.e., the SCC [12], the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [20], the Universal Image Quality Index (UIQI) [21] and the Gradient Magnitude Similarity Deviation (GMSD) [22]. All these metrics define in turn functionals enable of estimating f_{180} as for the TSI. In particular, for SCC, SSIM and UIQI the global maximum is of interest while for the GMSD the global minimum is relevant. Usually, to test a tomographic reconstruction strategy, two methods can be employed, i.e. testing the performance of the proposed approach on numerical phantoms and/or using standard real samples with known shape and refractive index values. Recently, a life-scale phantom with internal structures that mimics optical and structural properties of a biological sample has been proposed and fabricated by using the two-photon laser photolithography [23]. Here, to generate QPMs, we use a numerical phantom simulating the rotation of a flowing cell within the microfluidic channel. In particular, the numerical model of the 3D RI distribution of a cell is created by considering the main four sub-cellular structures, i.e., the cell membrane (RI = 1.350), the cytoplasm (RI = 1.365), the nucleus (RI = 1.380) and some mitochondria (RI = 1.410). The shapes of the structures and the corresponding nominal RIs are chosen by taking inspiration from measured values reported in literature for the MCF-7 cell line [24,25]. After the numerical integration of the 3D RI distribution along different orientations around the same axis and with fixed angular step, synthetic QPMs are obtained. To evaluate the accuracy and the robustness of the similarity metrics, we simulate 180 test cases, drawn by combining the following possibilities

- 2 possible Gaussian distributions of the RIs for each sub-cellular structure with average values corresponding to the nominal RIs reported above and standard deviations $\sigma_{RI} = \{0.01, 0.02\}$;
- 2 possible cell membrane structures, i.e., spherical and non-spherical;
- 5 possible cell rolling angles sets;
- 9 possible zero-mean Gaussian noises with standard deviations σ_N varying within $[0,0.2]$ rad with uniform step, added to each QPM.

Among the simulated rolling angles sets, three of them, with $\Delta\theta = \{3^\circ, 4^\circ, 5^\circ\}$, provide the exact 180° cell rotation at the frame $f_{180} = 61$, $f_{180} = 46$ and $f_{180} = 37$, respectively. The other two cases are designed by adding small perturbations on rolling angles created with $\Delta\theta = \{3^\circ, 5^\circ\}$, in order to simulate two angle sequences without the exact 180° cell rotation. In this case, similarity metrics must identify the frames with the rolling angles closer to 180° , which are 180.6° and 180.8° in such simulations. In Fig. 2(a), the numerical model of the 3D RI distribution of a cell obtained by simulating the nominal RI values is reported. Fig. 2(b,c) show the QPMs obtained from Fig. 2(a) by numerical integration along the orientations at 0° and 180° . In this example, the simulated angular step is $\Delta\theta = 3^\circ$, so the 180° of rotation occurs at frame $f_{180} = 61$. Fig. 2(d,e) report the corresponding noisy QPMs obtained by adding the Gaussian noise with $\sigma_N = 0.175$ rad in the case $\sigma_{RI} = 0.01$. Finally, Fig. 2(f) reports the SSC, SSIM, UIQI, GMSD and TSI similarity metrics, normalized to their respective maxima for visual comparison, for one of the considered test cases. In the legend, the estimated f_{180} of the five methods are reported. Notably, for the considered test case, TSI provides the right f_{180} showing also a sharp extreme point enabling the determination of f_{180} with a high reliability. The overall accuracy for each metric is now reported and indicated as A . The accuracy is calculated as the ratio between the number of correct identifications and the total number of test cases, i.e., 180. The correct identification consists of determining the frame with cell rotation equal to 180° when

$\Delta\theta = \{3^\circ, 4^\circ, 5^\circ\}$ or the one with cell rotation closest to 180° for the other two rolling angle sets. The results are $A_{TSI} = 98.33\%$, $A_{SSIM} = 80.56\%$, $A_{GMSD} = 79.44\%$, $A_{UIQI} = 77.22\%$ and $A_{SCC} = 67.78\%$.

Fig. 2. Numerical simulation to evaluate the performance of similarity metrics in f_{180} searching. (a) 3D RI distribution of an MCF-7 cell simulated with the nominal RI values and a non-spherical shape and (b,c) the corresponding QPMs obtained by numerical integration along the orientations at 0° and 180° (simulated angular step $\Delta\theta = 3^\circ$, then $f_{180} = 61$). (d,e) QPMs noisy images ($\sigma_N = 0.175$ rad) obtained in the case of $\sigma_{RI} = 0.01$. (f) Comparison among similarity metrics, normalized between 0 and 1. As reported in the legend, only TSI provides the right result, showing also a sharper extreme point than the other metrics.

As it can be seen, TSI shows the best results. It fails only in 3 cases, related to higher noise levels. However, in such cases, the error amounts at ± 1 frame. The other compared metrics show worse performances with the lowest accuracy reached by the SCC. One can expect this since the SCC has demonstrated to be efficient for non-spherical objects only [12,13]. It is important to underline that a wrong f_{180} estimation induces errors in any rolling angle and finally provokes artefacts in the tomographic reconstruction. To highlight such tomographic distortions, we perform tomographic reconstructions from the simulated QPMs sequence in Fig. 2(b,c) by using in Eq. (2) the rolling angles recovered by the considered similarity metrics. Moreover, we use a sequence of y positions by exploiting the assumed proportionality between translation and rotation. In particular, it is assumed that the particle translates of one pixel for a rotation of 0.1° . Fig. 3(a) illustrates the reference reconstruction in which the central slice is obtained by implementing the inverse Radon transform through the filtered back-projection algorithm [12,13] and achieved with the exact rolling angles. In Fig. 3(b), we report the same reconstruction but obtained by using the rolling angles estimated by the TSI. The considered test case is the one leading to a 180.6° cell rotation. In this case, TSI estimates as 180° the actual 180.6° rotation. A Root Mean Square Error ($RMSE_{RI} = 0.0007$) is obtained between the reference reconstruction and the reconstruction with recovered rolling angles. Finally, Fig. 3(c) shows the same reconstruction as before, but obtained when the rotation is estimated by SSIM, GMSD or UIQI. Indeed, the latter three methods achieve the same estimate $f_{180} = 60$, as it can be inferred from Fig. 2(f). Similarly, Fig. 3(d) displays the case when the rotation is evaluated by SCC for which $f_{180} = 58$. For both the considered reconstructions, lower and spreading RI values occur (see black arrows) as well as artefacts caused by the wrong estimations of f_{180} (violet arrows). $RMSE_{RI}$ increases of one order of magnitude with respect to TSI.

Fig. 3. Analysis of tomographic reconstructions quality with respect to the f_{180} estimation accuracy. (a) Reference reconstruction obtained with the exact rolling angles. (b) Reconstruction obtained with the rolling angles calculated with TSI. (c) Reconstruction with wrong estimations of f_{180} obtained with SSIM, UIQI, and GMSD. (d) Reconstruction obtained with SCC.

5. Experimental results and discussions

We report proof of concept experiments with the aim to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed rolling angle recovery method. In particular, we employ MCF-7 cells which flow and rotate in the microfluidic channel, covering full sample's rotation (i.e. 360°) within the FOV. The recording is made by a CCD with 35 fps, acquiring holographic sequences of 80-120 digital holograms per cell, depending on the position of the cells and their initial velocity. It is important to underline that, with our recording setting, we have an average rolling angle increment from 3° to 5° between two subsequent frames. Therefore, the acquisition of the digital hologram reporting the image of a cell rotated of exactly 180° with respect to the first recorded frame could be skipped. This confirms the need of an accurate metric able to precisely identify the frame of the closest rolling angle with respect to 180° . In the previous section, the proposed TSI has been demonstrated the best candidate to find such frame. Moreover, the precision of the holographic tracking is also crucial to minimize the estimation error of the entire rolling angles sequence by using Eq. (2). The combination of the automatic refocusing with TC and the weighted centroid for the transversal localization of cells has been demonstrated as one of the best solutions for holographic particles tracking [18]. In particular, the cell analysed in Fig. 4(a,b) is the one reported in Fig. 1(d), whose holographic tracking results have been shown in Fig. 1(e,f). The second cell in Fig. 4(c,d) is the most spherical one observed in our experiments and it has been selected to show how similarity metrics work for real spherical objects.

Fig. 4. Tomographic reconstructions of two MCF-7 cells. (a,c) TSI-based recovery method to identify the f_{180} frame and the corresponding QPMs. (b,d) 3D slice-by-slice tomographic reconstructions and corresponding iso-levels representations. The red circles in (a) and (c) highlight the frame f_{180} for the two cases.

Also in this case, position drifts along x and z axes are very limited, resulting in $\sigma_x = 0.13 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sigma_z = 0.48 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. the cell has quasi-constant positioning within the channel's cross section xz during the flow. The TSI curves are reported in Fig. 4(a,c), showing their global minima at the frames $f_{180} = 51$ and $f_{180} = 41$, respectively. Then, all the rolling angles are calculated through Eq. (2), thus obtaining that the highest cells orientations, corresponding to the rolling angles calculated at the last frames, are $\theta_K = 349.0^\circ$ and $\theta_K = 356.1^\circ$, with $K = 102$ and $K = 81$, respectively. The reconstructed phase images of the first frame of each sequence and the ones corresponding to the estimated 180° sample rotation are reported in insets within Fig. 4(a,c). Finally, tomographic reconstructions, obtained by using rolling angles sequences calculated with the proposed method, are shown in Fig. 4(b,d). In particular, the wide viewing angular interval and the accuracy in recovering rolling angles allow the recognition of small intracellular organelles in the iso-levels representations of tomograms (right sides of Fig. 4(b,d)). Finally, we evaluate tomographic reconstructions of both cells when other similarity metrics are used to calculate the rolling angles sequence. In Fig. 5, central slices of each tomogram are visually compared in order to detect artefacts each other. In particular, Fig. 5(a-c) and Fig. 5(j-l) report central slices of the reconstructed tomograms in Fig. 4(b,d), respectively. Notice that for the first cell (Fig. 5(a-c)) only TSI recovers $f_{180} = 51$, while SCC (Fig. 5(d-f)) provides $f_{180} = 49$. The proximity between these two estimated values implies a local variation of RI (see black arrows). Instead, other metrics provide a very different value with respect to TSI and SCC ($f_{180} = 58$, Fig. 5(g-i)), which causes large deviations in the tomogram. In fact, a wrong cell orientation is observed in Fig. 5(h), if compared to the same slices in Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 5(e). In the case of the second cell (Fig. 5(j-r)), three metrics, i.e. TSI, SSIM and UIQI, reach the same f_{180} value, equal to 41, while GMSD and SCC provide close values, i.e. $f_{180} = 39$ and $f_{180} = 43$, respectively. We highlight some artefacts within central slices in Fig. 5(m-r) but here the difference between tomograms seems to be limited to local RI variations only. In all cases, we evaluate the RMSE using the central slices obtained by the TSI as references. The worst value is obtained for the case in Fig. 5(h), as expected.

Fig. 5. Central slices visual comparison. (a,b,c) Central slices obtained from the tomogram in Fig.4(b) when the f_{180} value is estimated by using the TSI. (d,e,f) and (g,h,i) report the corresponding slices in the case of f_{180} provided by the SCC and by the other three metrics, i.e. SSIM, UIQI and GMSD. A large orientation artefact can be detected in (h). (j,k,l) Central slices obtained from the tomogram in Fig. 4(d). Here, three metrics reach the same f_{180} value, equal to 41. (m,n,o) and (p,q,r) report the corresponding slices in the case of f_{180} provided by the GMSD and SCC, respectively. Here, only local RI variations are detected.

6. Experimental results and discussions

In summary, we have proposed a new method to recover the rolling angles of cells, flowing in a microfluidic channel. A reliable retrieving of the rolling angles is needed for obtaining accurate tomographic reconstructions. The strategy is based on a new similarity metric, namely Tamura Similarity Index (TSI), able to identify the frame at which the 180° rotation occurs. Thanks to simulations, obtained by using a numerical phantom of a rolling cell with different shapes, RI distributions and noise levels, we have compared the results obtained with this metric with those achievable according to other commonly used similarity ones. The effectiveness and robustness of the proposed TSI has thus demonstrated. This occurs also for angle sequences without the exact 180° cell rotation. Once the 180° frame has been revealed, the rolling angles are accordingly calculated. Finally, we have provided two proof-of-concept experiments to test the proposed approach for tomographic reconstructions of MCF-7 cells. The results pave the way to the use of the proposed approach to the study of circulating cells. In fact, the proposed method, disregarding shapes and RI contents of cells, could be a good candidate to address the challenging problem of liquid biopsy, requesting the identification of circulating tumour cells within blood samples. Since the approach is amenable of parallel computing implementations [26], these new results can represent a relevant step towards a continuous flow cyto-tomography with the high-throughput is required.

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Disclosures

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